

A Review and Analysis of Crimes Against Women in India : A Geographical Perspective

Dr. Shweta Pandey *

Annu Priya**

Crimes against women represent a serious social problem in India, reflecting deep-rooted gender inequality, patriarchal social structures, and regional socio-economic disparities. During the last few decades, a growing body of literature has examined the nature, trends, and determinants of crimes against women at national and state levels. However, limited attention has been paid to micro-level spatial and temporal variations, particularly in backward regions. This review paper critically synthesizes findings from selected studies, including peer-reviewed journal articles, national crime reports, and policy documents, to examine crimes against women from a geographical perspective. Special emphasis is placed on spatio-temporal patterns, regional variations, and the application of GIS-based techniques in crime analysis. The review highlights significant gaps in district-level geographical research, especially with reference to backward regions. The paper concludes by emphasizing the need for localized spatio-temporal mapping to support evidence-based planning, policing, and gender-sensitive policy interventions.

Keywords: Crime, Women, Patriarchy, Domestic violence, Crime Geography.

Introduction : Crimes against women have emerged as a major concern across societies worldwide, transcending cultural, economic, and political boundaries. The United Nations defines violence against women as any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual, or psychological harm or suffering to women, whether occurring in public or private life (United Nations, 1993). In India, crimes against women are closely associated with patriarchal norms, gender discrimination, caste hierarchy, economic dependency, and unequal access to education and resources (Verma, 1990; Mukherjee et al., 2001).

According to the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), India continues to witness a rising trend in reported cases of crimes against women, including rape, domestic violence, dowry deaths, kidnapping, and sexual harassment.

Data published by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB 2020) reveal significant regional disparities in both the incidence and reporting of such crimes.

States such as Bihar, Orissa, west Bengal, UP, Haryana, Rajasthan faces compounded challenges due to poverty, low female literacy, unemployment, and weak institutional mechanisms, which further increase women's vulnerability to violence (NCRB, 2015-2020).

From a geographical perspective, crime is not randomly distributed across space and time. Human geographers argue that criminal activities exhibit distinct spatial patterns and temporal rhythms influenced by socio-economic conditions, population density, settlement structure, accessibility, and governance (Fyfe, 2000). However, most existing studies in India focus on national or state-level analysis, often overlooking micro-level variations at the district scale. Therefore, a systematic review of existing literature is essential to understand current trends,

* Sr. Assistant Professor, Jagjiwan Mahavidyalaya, Gaya, Email-pandeyshweta369@gmail.com

** Research Scholar, Magadh University, Bodhgaya, Email- annup9850@gmail.com

patterns and overall analysis of crimes against women in India.

The present review and analysis of CAW in India research study is reviewed, including peer-reviewed journal articles, government reports, and policy documents related to crimes against women. These studies were collected from academic databases such as Google Scholar, Research Gate, and official institutional websites.

The selection criteria included studies published between 2000 and 2024 that focused on crimes against women in India, with particular emphasis on spatial patterns, temporal trends, socio-economic determinants, and GIS-based analysis. Both qualitative and quantitative studies were considered to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the topic. The selected literature was systematically analyzed and categorized into thematic groups, including conceptual studies, national-level analyses, state and regional studies, and spatio-temporal research.

Thematic Review of Literature :

Conceptual and Theoretical Studies on Crimes Against Women : Several scholars have conceptualized crimes against women as a manifestation of patriarchal social structures, unequal power relations, and gender-based discrimination. Verma (1990) argues that violence against women in India is deeply embedded in patriarchal norms that subordinate women socially, economically, and politically. Mukherjee et al. (2001) further emphasize that crimes against women are influenced by caste hierarchy, social stratification, and cultural practices, making women from marginalized communities more vulnerable to violence.

International frame works, such as the United Nations Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women (United Nations, 1993), provide a comprehensive definition of gender-based violence and underline its universal nature. Reports by international organizations highlight that violence against women is not only a social issue but also a human rights concern, requiring multidimensional policy responses.

These conceptual studies provide a strong theoretical foundation for understanding crimes against women but largely lack spatial interpretation. Scholars also highlight key conceptual dimensions such as domestic and workplace discrimination, disparities in education, economy, politics, and culture, psychological factors, lack of self-awareness, and limited knowledge of constitutional rights. Although these studies provide a strong theoretical foundation, they largely lack spatial and temporal interpretation. The absence of geographical perspectives underscores the need to integrate socio-cultural theories with spatial analysis to better understand the distribution and intensity of crimes against women.

Literature consistently identifies socio-economic factors such as poverty, unemployment, low literacy, caste discrimination, and gender inequality as major determinants of crimes against women. Studies suggest that women's economic dependency and lack of education increase their vulnerability to domestic violence and exploitation. Cultural norms that normalize male dominance further contribute to underreporting and tolerance of violence. These determinants vary spatially across regions, influencing the distribution and intensity of crimes against women. However, most studies examine these factors independently, without integrating them into a comprehensive spatial-temporal frame work. This limitation restricts the ability to understand how socio-economic variables interact with spatial patterns of crime.

Several empirical studies have established a strong relationship between economic stress and violence against women. Anderberg and Wadsworth (2013) demonstrated that male unemployment significantly increases the incidence of domestic violence, particularly in households experiencing financial insecurity. The study argues that economic instability intensifies power imbalance within families, often resulting in aggressive behavior against

women. Similarly, Amaral (2021) examined the relationship between gender, crime, and punishment and found that women face structural disadvantages not only as victims of crime but also within justice delivery mechanisms. Economic vulnerability, limited access to legal support, and delayed judicial processes further weaken women's ability to seek protection. These findings indicate that crimes against women are deeply intertwined with broader economic conditions, which vary spatially across regions. From a geographical perspective, areas characterized by high unemployment, poverty, and informal labour are more likely to experience higher levels of domestic and gender-based violence. However, most existing studies do not spatially map economic vulnerability alongside crime patterns, highlighting a major research gap. (Anderberg & Wadsworth, 2013; Amaral, 2021)

Beyond household-level violence, several studies emphasize structural and cultural dimensions of crimes against women. Gangoli (2011) argues that violence against women in India often functions as a mechanism to control women's sexuality and reinforce patriarchal authority. Practices such as honour-based violence, moral policing, and restrictions on women's mobility contribute to both visible and invisible forms of violence. Fairbairn (2015) examined sexual threats and rape as instruments of revenge and domination, particularly in socially unstable environments. Such violence is frequently symbolic, aimed at humiliating women and asserting male power. These forms of violence are often underreported, making spatial documentation extremely limited. Studies on conflict and insurgency further reveal heightened vulnerability of women during political instability. Research on women and insurgency (Group, 2019) highlights how conflict situations increase sexual violence, displacement, and exploitation of women, especially in regions with weak governance structures. Eboe-Osuji (2012) conceptualized forced marriage as a form of structural violence and a violation of fundamental human rights. Although largely discussed in international literature, similar practices exist in parts of India in the form of early marriage and socially coerced unions, which remain spatially undocumented.

These studies collectively indicate that crimes against women extend beyond individual acts and are embedded within social, cultural, and political structures. However, the absence of spatial-temporal mapping of such structural violence remains a significant limitation in existing geographical research. (Gangoli, 2011; Fairbairn, 2015; Group, 2019; Eboe-Osuji, 2012)

National-Level Studies and pattern of Crimes Against Women in India : National-level studies show that crimes against women in India have increased significantly over the last two decades, both in terms of total reported cases and crime rates. According to the analysis of NCRB data presented by Ghai (2024), reported cases increased from 143,795 in 2000 to 405,861 in 2020, reflecting a 182.1 percent rise over twenty years. This sharp increase indicates that gender-based violence remains a serious and persistent problem across the country. The growth is not confined to one region but is visible across northern, central, western, and southern states. State-wise trends reveal even sharper increases in specific regions. Uttar Pradesh reported 18,711 cases in 2000, which increased to 59,853 cases in 2020, showing a 219.8 percent rise (Ghai, 2024). Delhi recorded 4,032 cases in 2000 and 12,902 cases in 2020, representing a 219.9 percent increase. Maharashtra showed an increase from 15,459 cases in 2000 to 37,144 cases in 2020, a rise of 140.2 percent (Ghai, 2024). These figures show that highly populated and urbanised states continue to report large numbers of crimes against women. Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh also consistently appear among high-incidence states, especially in crimes such as rape, kidnapping, and domestic violence (Pooja et al., 2024).

At the national level, the crime rate per lakh women increased from 57 in 2020 to 67 in 2022, indicating a rapid rise within a short period (Pooja et al., 2024). This period also coincided with the COVID-19 pandemic, during which mobility restrictions and economic stress may have increased domestic violence. Murmu (2022) argues that socio-economic stress, unemployment, and confinement within households contributed to a rise in intimate partner violence during the pandemic years. The study further highlights that states with high population density and economic inequality showed sharper increases in reported domestic violence cases.

Category-wise distribution provides deeper understanding of the pattern. In 2020, cruelty by husband and relatives accounted for 125,298 cases, forming 30.9 percent of total crimes against women (Ghai, 2024). Rape cases were recorded at 32,033 (7.9 percent), sexual harassment at 25,255 (6.2 percent), and dowry-related deaths and harassment together formed a significant share. These figures clearly show that domestic violence remains the dominant category across India. Murmu (2022) also emphasizes that domestic violence is often underreported in rural and economically weaker regions due to social stigma and dependence on family structures. Therefore, actual incidence may be higher than reported numbers.

Regional variation is clearly visible when southern states are examined separately. According to Sarkar (2024), Andhra Pradesh reported 25,503 total crimes against women in 2022, while Telangana recorded a crime rate of 117 per lakh women, which is significantly above the national average. Kerala recorded 82 per lakh women, Karnataka 53.6 per lakh, and Tamil Nadu 24 per lakh (Sarkar, 2024). These differences show that even within relatively developed southern states, crime levels are uneven. Telangana's high rate indicates that rapid urbanisation and economic growth do not automatically reduce violence.

Official Kerala Police data for the period 2020–2025 further illustrates temporal change at the state level (Kerala Police, 2026). Total reported crimes increased from 12,659 cases in 2020 to 16,199 in 2021 and further to 18,943 in 2022. In 2023, cases were 18,980, and in 2024 they were 18,887, followed by a slight decline to 18,035 in 2025. This shows a sharp increase between 2020 and 2022, followed by stabilisation. Rape cases showed a steady increase during this period, while cruelty by husband remained one of the largest categories. Dowry deaths remained comparatively low, often in single digits annually, which contrast with higher dowry-related cases reported in northern states.

The comparison between developed and less developed states presents an important contradiction. Himabindu et al. (2014) observed that states with higher Human Development Index (HDI) values also report significant levels of crimes against women. This suggests that development indicators such as literacy, income, and health do not automatically ensure women's safety. Similarly, Chakraborty et al. (2021) found a nonlinear relationship between economic growth and crime, suggesting that crime may initially increase during periods of economic transition and urbanization. Varma (2023) further argues that economic development can increase women's public participation, workforce mobility, and visibility, which may lead to higher reporting of harassment and assault cases. Therefore, higher crime numbers in developed states may partly reflect improved reporting and greater awareness rather than only higher violence.

Spatial hotspot analysis also confirms clustering of crimes in specific regions. Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Haryana, Telangana, and Odisha have been identified as significant hotspots between 2020 and 2022 (Pooja et al., 2024). These states show concentration of rape, kidnapping, and domestic violence cases. Northern states such as Uttar Pradesh continue to report the highest total numbers due to their large population base. However, when crime rates per lakh population are considered, smaller states such as

Telangana may appear more vulnerable.

Northeastern states such as Sikkim, Nagaland, and Mizoram report lower incidence rates (Ghai, 2024). However, researchers caution that cultural factors, community-based dispute resolution systems, and underreporting may influence official statistics. Murmu (2022) highlights that social stigma, fear of family dishonour, and lack of institutional access prevent many women from reporting violence, especially in rural and tribal areas.

Overall, data from 2000 to 2025 clearly indicates a sustained upward trend in crimes against women across India. The 182.1 percent increase over two decades, the more than 219 percent rise in states like Uttar Pradesh and Delhi, the increase in national crime rate from 57 to 67 per lakh within two years, and the steady rise in Kerala from 12,659 cases in 2020 to nearly 19,000 cases in 2022 together demonstrate that gender-based violence remains widespread. Domestic violence continues to account for nearly one-third of total cases nationally. Regional concentration, socio-economic inequality, urbanisation, and patriarchal norms collectively influence these patterns.

Therefore, national and state-level evidence suggests that crimes against women in India are shaped by both structural and contextual factors. Economic development, literacy, and urban growth alone have not eliminated violence. Instead, a combination of improved reporting mechanisms, socio-economic stress, demographic pressure, and persistent gender inequality continues to shape the observed trends. Understanding these spatial and temporal patterns is essential for designing targeted interventions, strengthening enforcement mechanisms, and developing region-specific policy responses.

Critical Synthesis of the Reviewed Studies : The critical examination of the selected twenty seven studies reveals several important patterns, strengths, and limitations in existing research on crimes against women. A careful review of existing studies on crimes against women in India shows a broad agreement that such crimes are closely linked with patriarchal social structures, socio-economic inequality, and weak institutional support systems. Most scholars recognize that gender-based violence is not merely an individual or legal issue but a structural problem shaped by social norms, economic dependency, caste hierarchy, and unequal access to education and resources.

National-level studies, mainly based on NCRB data, provide useful information on the overall magnitude, major categories, and long-term trends of crimes against women. These studies clearly indicate a rising trend in reported cases over time. Researchers explain this increase as a combined effect of actual growth in crime, improved reporting, greater awareness among women, and legal reforms. However, such studies largely remain descriptive and present data at aggregated levels, which often hides important variations within states and districts.

State-level and regional studies add valuable insights by linking crime patterns with local socio-economic and cultural conditions. Studies focusing on less developed and less literate states highlight the role of poverty, unemployment, low female literacy, and deeply rooted patriarchal values in increasing women's vulnerability. At the same time, research on more developed states suggests that higher crime figures may also reflect better reporting and access to institutions. Despite their strengths, most regional studies rely on simple statistical analysis and do not adequately capture micro-level spatial differences.

A limited number of studies use spatial-temporal and GIS-based methods to analyze crimes against women. These studies show that crimes are spatially concentrated in specific locations rather than being randomly distributed. While GIS-based approaches offer strong analytical potential, their application is mostly restricted to metropolitan areas or selected case

studies. Backward and semi-urban regions, especially in states like Bihar, remain largely unexplored.

Overall, the reviewed literature highlights important trends and causes of crimes against women but also reveals clear gaps. The lack of district-level studies, limited use of spatial–temporal techniques, and weak integration of socio-economic factors restrict a deeper understanding of localized crime patterns. These limitations underline the need for more focused geographical research at the district level to support effective planning, policing, and gender-sensitive policy interventions.

Conclusion and discussion : This review highlights that crimes against women in India remain a serious concern despite constitutional and legal safeguards. Existing studies consistently show a rising trend in reported cases, driven by both an actual increase in crime and improved reporting due to greater awareness and legal reforms. However, most national-level analyses rely on aggregated data, which often conceals important regional and local variations.

State and regional studies reveal that socio-economic backwardness, low female literacy, poverty, unemployment, and entrenched patriarchal norms increase women's vulnerability, particularly in less developed regions. Although spatial–temporal and GIS-based studies demonstrate that crimes against women are spatially concentrated rather than randomly distributed, such approaches are limited in number and largely focused on metropolitan areas.

Overall, the literature lacks district-level and integrated spatial analysis linking crime patterns with socio-economic factors. This gap underlines the need for localized spatio-temporal geographical studies, especially in backward regions like Gaya district, to support evidence-based planning, effective policing, and gender-sensitive policy interventions.

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